

Implicit Capture at the Macroscopic Level for Variance Reduction in Monte Carlo Transport

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ABSTRACT

This study introduces a new variance reduction method for Monte Carlo transport calculations, termed macroscopic implicit capture. Unlike conventional implicit capture, where the particle's surviving weight is computed after the selection of the collision nuclide at every collision, the proposed method determines the weight of the surviving particle at the macroscopic level—that is, prior to nuclide selection. This fundamental change is designed to achieve effective variance reduction by eliminating the uncertainty associated with the surviving weight.

To provide a theoretical basis for this advancement, we extend Booth's variance formulation, which was originally derived for an infinite one-group homogeneous medium. It accurately accounts for explicit nuclide selection and absolute weight cutoffs within the original idealized problem, and allows the comparison of the variance and efficiency of the proposed macroscopic scheme with conventional implicit capture and analog capture methods. The theoretical predictions for both variance and calculation time from the extended formulation were then verified using controlled Monte Carlo calculations.

The practical effectiveness of the macroscopic implicit capture method is thoroughly confirmed through its application to a continuous-energy pin-cell problem. The results consistently demonstrate a significant improvement in the Figure of Merit (FOM) compared to conventional approaches, with appropriate adjustment of the cutoff weight. These compelling theoretical and numerical findings collectively establish that the proposed macroscopic implicit capture scheme offers enhanced performance and efficiency in Monte Carlo transport, presenting a valuable advancement for high-fidelity simulations.

Keywords: Implicit Capture, Survival Biasing, Variance Reduction, Figure of Merit (FOM), Analytic Formulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Implicit capture, also known as survival biasing, is a standard variance reduction technique applied in many established Monte Carlo neutron transport codes, including MCNP [1], Tripoli-4 [2], and McCARD [3]. Unlike analog capture, which simulates absorption reactions (capture and fission) probabilistically, implicit capture ensures the neutron always survives a collision by reducing its weight to the expected surviving weight. This non-analog method is known for producing unbiased results [4].

Implicit capture offers two primary advantages. First, it increases tally efficiency by ensuring particles that reach a region of interest are not lost immediately before tallying [1]. Second, the application of the expected surviving weight reduces the history variance overall [2]. The foundational analytical formulation detailing the effects of implicit capture on computational time and the variance of tally

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estimators was originally derived by Booth and Cashwell for an infinite one-group homogeneous medium [5].

Conventionally, implicit capture is applied after the collision nuclide has been selected, using the microscopic cross section of that nuclide to determine the surviving particle weight. In this work, we propose a new approach, referred to as macroscopic implicit capture. In this scheme, the expected surviving weight is determined prior to nuclide selection, based on the macroscopic cross section summed over all nuclides. The core premise of the proposed scheme is to reduce uncertainty by removing variations in the resulting particle weight that stem from the probabilistic selection of the collision nuclide.

To support the proposed method, we extend Booth's analytical variance formulation to incorporate the effects of explicit collision nuclide selection and absolute weight cutoff. The extended formulation is derived specifically based on the conventional implicit capture scheme, but it can be readily simplified to describe both analog and the proposed macroscopic implicit capture schemes. Additionally, we formulate the expected computational time by assuming it is proportional to the total number of collisions. The derived formulation for both variance and calculation time are verified through infinite one-group Monte Carlo calculations across all three capture schemes. Finally, the practical effectiveness of the method is evaluated through Monte Carlo simulations of a continuous-energy pin-cell problem, where the Figure of Merit (FOM) of the multiplication factor tally is compared to assess the performance against conventional approaches.

2. Derivation of the Variance Formulation

This section presents the analytical derivation of the variance formulation for conventional implicit capture. The variance formulation is derived for the neutron multiplication factor (k_{eff}) utilizing the collision estimator. The formulation is first derived for an infinite one-group medium with an endless collision sequence (i.e., without weight cutoff). This resulting formulation is then to rigorously incorporate the effects of an absolute weight cutoff, and to deduce the macroscopic implicit capture algorithm for variance reduction.

2.1. Variance Formulation for Conventional Implicit Capture under the Endless Collision Sequence

Let i denote the nuclide index. We define C_i as the event that the i -th nuclide is selected as the collision nuclide, represented by an indicator variable:

$$C_i \equiv \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the } i\text{-th nuclide is selected} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (1)$$

The probability p_i corresponding to each event C_i is determined as follows:

$$p_i = \frac{\Sigma_{t,i}}{\Sigma_t}, \quad (2)$$

where $\Sigma_{t,i}$ is the macroscopic total cross section for the i -th nuclide, and Σ_t is the macroscopic total cross section summed over all nuclides.

According to the conventional implicit capture scheme, the particle's weight is reduced by the following ratio r_i after the collision event C_i :

$$r_i \equiv \frac{\sigma_{t,i} - \sigma_{\gamma,i} - \sigma_{f,i}}{\sigma_{t,i}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{t,i}$ is the microscopic total cross section for the i -th nuclide, and $\sigma_{\gamma,i}$, $\sigma_{f,i}$ are the microscopic capture and fission cross sections for the i -th nuclide respectively.

We define $K_0(w_0 \rightarrow 0)$ as a random variable representing the contribution to k_{eff} , estimated by the collision estimator during an infinite number of collisions that reduces the particle's weight from w_0 to zero. It satisfies the following recursive equation:

$$K_0(w_0 \rightarrow 0) = \frac{\nu \Sigma_f}{\Sigma_t} w_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N C_i K_0(r_i w_0 \rightarrow 0), \quad (4)$$

where N is the total number of nuclides. The summation with indicator variable C_i indicates that, although all nuclides are present as potential candidates for a collision event, only one of them is actually occurred.

By applying the method of undetermined coefficients, the expected value of $K_0(w_0 \rightarrow 0)$ can be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} E[K_0(w_0 \rightarrow 0)] &= \frac{\nu \Sigma_f}{\Sigma_t} \frac{1}{1 - \mu_r} w_0 \\ &= k_0 w_0, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\mu_r \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N p_i r_i = \frac{\Sigma_t - \Sigma_\gamma - \Sigma_f}{\Sigma_t}, \quad (6)$$

representing the expected value of the weight reduction ratio r_i , or equivalently, the expected surviving probability for a single collision, and k_0 represents the first mode eigenvalue.

In a similar manner, the variance of $K_0(w_0 \rightarrow 0)$ can also be obtained as follows:

$$V[K_0(w_0 \rightarrow 0)] = \left(\frac{(1 + \mu_r)(1 - \mu_r)}{1 - \mu_r^{(2)}} - 1 \right) k_0^2 w_0^2. \quad (7)$$

where

$$\mu_r^{(2)} \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N p_i r_i^2, \quad (8)$$

representing the second moment of the weight reduction ratio.

The recursive approach of solving the first and the second moment has been demonstrated in previous studies [5-6]. Eq. (7) demonstrates that this approach can resolve the variance through the introduction of μ_r and $\mu_r^{(2)}$, even in systems where an explicit collision nuclide is present.

2.2. Extension of the Variance Formulation to Incorporate Absolute Weight Cutoff

To prevent particles from being simulated indefinitely, Russian roulette based on particle's weight is essential to the implicit capture scheme. T. E. Booth assumed that both the cutoff weight and the recovered weight for Russian roulette are proportional to the particle's initial weight [5]. P. K. Sarkar and M. A. Prasad considered a system where the recovered weight is proportional to the particle's weight entering the Russian roulette [6]. Differences in the modeling of Russian roulette into previously derived variance formulations affect their resulting expressions.

In our formulation, we consider a system with an absolute cutoff weight and a recovered weight, which are fixed and independent of the particle's initial or current weight. The probabilistic formulation of the Russian roulette procedure is given as follows:

$$w_{RR} = \begin{cases} w_e, & \text{with probability } p = \tilde{w} / w_e \text{ for } \tilde{w} < w_{co}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where w_{RR} is resulting weight after Russian roulette, \tilde{w} is the weight entering Russian roulette, w_{co} is the cutoff weight, and w_e is the restored weight if the particle survives the procedure. For simplicity, we set $w_e = 1$, which allows the Russian roulette procedure to be represented as a Bernoulli trial as follows:

$$w_{RR} = \text{Bernoulli}(\tilde{w}) \text{ for } \tilde{w} < w_{co}, \quad (10)$$

where $\text{Bernoulli}(\tilde{w})$ is a Bernoulli trial with success probability \tilde{w} .

When the weight cutoff is imposed, the collision sequence is truncated accordingly. Therefore, in systems where Russian roulette is present, the previous recursive relation no longer holds. Let \tilde{w}_j denote the possible values of \tilde{w} resulting from collision sequences starting from $w_0 = 1$, and let q_j be the probability of drawing a sequence that yields \tilde{w}_j , where j indexes the possible values of \tilde{w} . Let $K_0(1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j)$ denote the contribution from a particle starting at unit weight, until truncated by the cutoff condition at $\tilde{w} = \tilde{w}_j$, and let $K_0(1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j)$ denote the contribution that the collision sequence reaches but not be stopped at $\tilde{w} = \tilde{w}_j$, continued infinitely after \tilde{w}_j . Then, the expected value and variance of $K_0(1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j)$ can be decomposed as follows:

$$E[K_0(1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j)] = E[K_0(1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j)] - E[K_0(\tilde{w}_j \rightarrow 0)], \quad (11)$$

$$V[K_0(1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j)] = V[K_0(1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j)] - V[K_0(\tilde{w}_j \rightarrow 0)]. \quad (12)$$

Conditioning the collision sequence on $\tilde{w} = \tilde{w}_j$ imposes a restriction on the nuclide selection, thereby introducing a bias relative to the unconstrained case. Therefore, it should be noted that $K_0(1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j)$ differs significantly from $K_0(1 \rightarrow 0)$, thus, Eqs. (11) and (12) no longer hold in the unconstrained case. Even so, generalizing the formulation to $K_0(1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j)$ for arbitrary \tilde{w}_j remains highly challenging and futile. At this point, we instead approach the problem through the statistical characteristics of \tilde{w}_j , rather than formulating each $K_0(1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j)$ individually.

Given an arbitrary cutoff system, any collision sequence yields a uniquely determined value of \tilde{w} . Therefore, sampling a collision sequence can be regarded as first drawing \tilde{w} from the underlying distribution \mathcal{W} , and then determining the corresponding conditional sequence. Then the following relation holds:

$$K_0(1 \rightarrow 0) = \sum_j I_j K_0(1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j), \quad (13)$$

where I_j is an indicator variable that denotes whether \tilde{w}_j is drawn, defined as follows:

$$I_j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \tilde{w}_j \text{ is drawn with probability } q_j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Taking the expectation of \tilde{w}_j in Eqs. (11) and (12) yields the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{\tilde{w}} \left[E \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right] &= E_{\tilde{w}} \left[E \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right] - E_{\tilde{w}} \left[E \left[K_0 (\tilde{w}_j \rightarrow 0) \right] \right] \\
 &= E \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow 0) \right] - \sum_j q_j E \left[K_0 (\tilde{w}_j \rightarrow 0) \right] \\
 &= k_0 (1 - \mu_w),
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{\tilde{w}} \left[V \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right] &= E_{\tilde{w}} \left[V \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right] - E_{\tilde{w}} \left[V \left[K_0 (\tilde{w}_j \rightarrow 0) \right] \right] \\
 &= V \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow 0) \right] - V_{\tilde{w}} \left[E \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right] - E_{\tilde{w}} \left[V \left[K_0 (\tilde{w}_j \rightarrow 0) \right] \right] \\
 &= \left(\frac{(1 + \mu_r)(1 - \mu_r)}{1 - \mu_r^{(2)}} - 1 \right) k_0^2 (1 - \mu_w^{(2)}) - V_{\tilde{w}} \left[E \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right],
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

where

$$\mu_w \equiv \sum_j q_j \tilde{w}_j, \quad \mu_w^{(2)} \equiv \sum_j q_j \tilde{w}_j^2. \tag{17}$$

Now let K be a random variable denoting the total contribution to k_{eff} from a single particle starting with $w_0 = 1$, including Russian roulette. It can be expressed as follows:

$$K = \sum_j I_j \left(K_0 (1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j) + \text{Bernoulli}(\tilde{w}_j) \tilde{K} \right), \tag{18}$$

where \tilde{K} is an independent copy of K .

The expected value and the variance of K can be obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E[K] &= \sum_j E \left[I_j \left(K_0 (1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j) + \text{Bernoulli}(\tilde{w}_j) \tilde{K} \right) \right] \\
 &= \sum_j q_j \left(E \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j) \right] + E \left[\text{Bernoulli}(\tilde{w}_j) \tilde{K} \right] \right) \\
 &= k_0 (1 - \mu_w) + \mu_w E[K],
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$E[K] = k_0. \tag{20}$$

and,

$$\begin{aligned}
 V[K] &= E_{\tilde{w}} \left[V \left[K | \tilde{w}_j \right] \right] + V_{\tilde{w}} \left[E \left[K | \tilde{w}_j \right] \right] \\
 &= E_{\tilde{w}} \left[V \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j) \right] + V \left[\text{Bernoulli}(\tilde{w}_j) \tilde{K} \right] + V_{\tilde{w}} \left[E \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right] \right] \\
 &= E_{\tilde{w}} \left[V \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow \tilde{w}_j | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right] + \mu_w V[K] + \left(\mu_w - \mu_w^{(2)} \right) k_0^2 + V_{\tilde{w}} \left[E \left[K_0 (1 \rightarrow 0 | \tilde{w}_j) \right] \right] \\
 &= \left(\frac{(1 + \mu_r)(1 - \mu_r)}{1 - \mu_r^{(2)}} - 1 \right) k_0^2 (1 - \mu_w^{(2)}) + \mu_w V[K] + \left(\mu_w - \mu_w^{(2)} \right) k_0^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

$$V[K] = k_0^2 \left(\left(\frac{(1 + \mu_r)(1 - \mu_r)}{1 - \mu_r^{(2)}} - 1 \right) X_w + Y_w \right), \tag{22}$$

where

$$X_w \equiv \frac{1 - \mu_w^{(2)}}{1 - \mu_w}, Y_w \equiv \frac{\mu_w - \mu_w^{(2)}}{1 - \mu_w}. \quad (23)$$

The final expression in Eq. (22) holds for any arbitrary cutoff system, thus w_{co} in our system is not explicitly included in the formulation. Nevertheless, it remains a major contributor to the variance by constraining $\mu_w < w_{co}$ and $\mu_w^{(2)} < w_{co}^2$. Note that the case where $w_{co} = 1$ is equivalent to analog capture, since Russian roulette is performed after every collision with a survival probability identical to the non-absorption probability in analog capture.

2.3. Macroscopic Implicit Capture Algorithm

As shown in Eq. (22), a smaller $\mu_r^{(2)}$ leads to lower variance. It is minimized when r_i is constant for all nuclide indices i . Here, we propose an algorithm that performs implicit capture in a manner independent of the selected nuclide—i.e., at the macroscopic level—while preserving the μ_r and the scattering probability for each nuclide, thus yielding results equivalent to those of conventional implicit capture. The algorithm consists of the following three steps:

Algorithm: Macroscopic Implicit Capture

1. Reduce the particle weight by a factor of μ_r , which is computed from Eq. (6).
2. Select the collision nuclide based on probabilities excluding capture and fission reactions:

$$p_i^* = \frac{\Sigma_{t,i} - \Sigma_{\gamma,i} - \Sigma_{f,i}}{\Sigma_t - \Sigma_{\gamma} - \Sigma_f} \quad (24)$$

3. Perform the elastic/inelastic scattering reaction.

The proposed macroscopic implicit capture scheme reduces the particle weight regardless of the nuclide selected, thus minimizing the $\mu_r^{(2)}$ and the resulting variance.

2.4. Formulation for the Calculation Time

To incorporate computational time into the formulation, an approach that assumes it to be proportional to the number of events (free-flight and collision) was proposed by T. E. Booth [5]. Accordingly, we follow the same approach and further assume that the computational time scales with the number of collisions only, as the formulation represents a collision estimator in an infinite medium.

Let T be a random variable denoting the total collision number from a single particle starting with $w_0 = 1$, including Russian roulette. Using Wald's equation from renewal theory [7], The expected value of T can be obtained in the same manner, as follows:

$$E[T] = \frac{1}{1 - \mu_w} \frac{E_{\tilde{w}}[\log \tilde{w}_j]}{E[\log r_i]}. \quad (25)$$

3. Numerical Results

3.1. Infinite One-Group Problem

Verification of the formulations are performed through Monte Carlo simulations using 100 million particle histories. The Monte Carlo-estimated values of the variance of k_{eff} , and the total number of collisions, respectively—are compared with the values obtained from the analytical formulations. Each of the three schemes—Conventional Implicit Capture, Analog Capture, and Macroscopic Implicit Capture—was individually verified against the derived formulation. Table 1 provides the specifications of the infinite one-group problem in terms of macroscopic cross sections per nuclide. Inelastic scattering

reactions that generate surplus particles are not considered; thus, only elastic scattering is considered. The problem represents a case where the weight reduction ratio r_i vary significantly across nuclides.

A cutoff weight of $w_{co}=0.25$ is used for both the conventional and macroscopic implicit capture schemes, while μ_w and $\mu_w^{(2)}$ are tallied during the Monte Carlo calculations. Tables 2 present comparisons between the predicted values from the formulation and the Monte Carlo results for the relative variance of k_{eff} , and the total number of collisions respectively. The results verify that the proposed formulations yield predictions that are in exact agreement with the simulation results in all cases. Furthermore, the collision-based performance indicator is defined in Eq. (26), to evaluate the performance in the formulation,

$$FOM_{col} = \frac{1}{R^2 N_{col}}, \quad (26)$$

where R is the relative standard deviation, and N_{col} is the total number of collisions. The macroscopic implicit capture scheme exhibits approximately 60% higher performance than the conventional implicit capture scheme.

Table I. Specifications of the Infinite One-Group Problem

Nuclide	Σ_γ	Σ_f	Σ_t	ν
1H	1.45×10^{-3}	-	4.45×10^{-1}	-
8O	7.39×10^{-5}	-	1.08×10^{-1}	-
^{235}U	2.35×10^{-3}	1.15×10^{-2}	1.55×10^{-2}	2.4×10^0
^{238}U	7.07×10^{-3}	7.17×10^{-4}	8.36×10^{-2}	2.4×10^0

Table II. Verification of the Formulation using Monte Carlo Simulation

Method	Relative Variance of k_{eff}		Total Number of Collisions		Performance Indicator
	Predicted	MC Result	Predicted	MC Result	
Analog Capture	9.64×10^{-9}	9.64×10^{-9}	2.82×10^9	2.82×10^9	3.68×10^{-2}
Conventional Implicit Capture	4.92×10^{-9}	4.92×10^{-9}	4.09×10^9	4.09×10^9	4.97×10^{-2}
Macroscopic Implicit Capture	2.44×10^{-9}	2.44×10^{-9}	5.16×10^9	5.16×10^9	7.94×10^{-2}

3.2. Continuous Energy Pin-Cell Problem

The performance of the Macroscopic Implicit Capture (MIC) method is evaluated for a continuous-energy UO_2 pin-cell problem, using McCARD [3]. The simulations are carried out with 10,000 particles over 500 active cycles, for both conventional and macroscopic implicit capture method. The FOM is defined in Eq. (27), to evaluate the performance,

$$FOM = \frac{1}{R^2 T}, \quad (27)$$

where R is the relative standard deviation, and T is the total calculation time. Figure 1 shows the FOM for the two schemes as a function of the cutoff weight. At $w_{co} = 0.25$, the macroscopic implicit capture exhibited 1.54 times FOM that of the conventional implicit capture. Moreover, as w_{co} decreases, the FOM of the macroscopic implicit capture continues to increase, unlike that of the conventional implicit

capture, reaching an optimum near $w_{co} = 0.025$. At this point, the FOM is 2.5 times higher than the FOM of the conventional implicit capture at its highest value, which occurred at $w_{co} = 0.25$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study derived a variance formulation under the implicit capture scheme using an infinite one-group problem, and based on this, we proposed a new variance reduction method called the Macroscopic Implicit Capture (MIC) scheme. The formulation was verified by demonstrating its ability to accurately predict the variances for all three schemes and the predicted variance reduction trends were confirmed. To evaluate the applicability of the proposed method, a continuous-energy pin-cell problem was computed, and the results showed that the MIC scheme effectively improves computational efficiency by increasing the Figure of Merit (FOM). One of the key advantages of the proposed scheme is its simplicity in implementation. It merely shifts the region in which implicit capture occurs to the macroscopic level, a feature made possible because capture reactions yield the same outcome regardless of which nuclide is selected. By eliminating the uncertainty in the particle's weight after a collision, the method significantly contributes to overall variance reduction, and we anticipate that this approach will find widespread use as an effective means to improve the efficiency of Monte Carlo simulations.

Figure 1. FOM with Cutoff Weight

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